

Magnetic composite based on ABS polymer and iron powder for fused deposition modeling

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ABSTRACT

Additive manufacturing (AM) is a modern technology that allows to fabricate complex products from various materials and has many advantages compared to traditional production methods. Magnetic materials are related to many essential applications. They are key components of motors, generators, transformers, magnetic-coolers, and many others. In this work, we present research on a magnetic composite designed for AM. The composite material with magnetic properties was prepared from acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) and iron (Fe). The components in various ratios (Fe powder from 50% to 75%) were mixed mechanically and thermally compounded through a single-screw extruder. The physical properties of composites were investigated by X-ray diffraction, density, electron microscopy, magnetization, specific heat, electrical conductivity, and mechanical properties measurements. Structural measurements showed that Fe particles do not agglomerate or oxidize during the composite synthesis process. Ferromagnetic properties of developed materials were examined. The

electrical resistance of the resulting materials is at 10^{12} Ω/cm , two orders of magnitude lower than for pure ABS. The results were compared with those obtained for a commercially available polylactide-based (PLA) material. Finally, 1.75 mm diameter filament was fabricated and the objects were printed using the fused deposition modeling (FDM) technique. Working electronic devices were built from the 3D printed elements.

Keywords: Additive manufacturing, Fused deposition modeling, Composites, Functional filaments, Soft magnetic materials

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Introduction

Additive manufacturing (AM) is a rapidly emerging technology for building objects. It offers many advantages compared to traditional manufacturing techniques. Traditional manufacturing methods will not disappear completely, and AM should be considered a complementary form of object manufacturing. One type of AM is 3D printing [1]. The 3D printing process can be carried out using several technologies. One of the most popular is fused deposition modeling (FDM), in which material in the form of a filament is heated by the print head and then layer by layer is placed on a heated table [2].

3D printing technology finds applications in various fields of engineering, among others in rapid prototyping of simple mechanical components, manufacturing components of magnetic circuits for energy conversion and sensing applications [3] as well as for bioengineering [4]. There are increasing number of application of AM to print components of magnetic circuits [5–7]. Magnetic materials have numerous applications in everyday devices, making the introduction of AM in their production significant [8]. Traditional methods of manufacturing magnetic circuits are multi-step and complex, therefore the use of AM for magnetic circuits can positively impact the entire industry [9]. There are already various examples of this technology using magnetic materials for different applications. The technology can be used to produce permanent magnets [10,11], biocompatible nanomagnetite-based composites [12], soft magnetic robots [13], as well as magnetocaloric materials [14]. The magnetocaloric effect, which involves changing the temperature of a magnetic material using an external magnetic field, can be utilized to develop new types of thermal devices such as refrigerators, heat pumps, air conditioners, and gas condensers. 3D printing can help create components in the right shape for proper heat exchange and improve the prototyping process.

The increasing interest in AM technology and the demand for new printable materials, were motivation to develop a composite with magnetic properties suited for FDM 3D printing. Our composite is based on acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) copolymer, which is a widely used printing material. ABS is known for its amorphous structure and excellent mechanical properties [15]. We also included pure iron as the second component, which is the most popular magnetic material

[16]. This composite opens up new possibilities for constructing devices and research in the field. In our study, we created several composites with different ratios, thoroughly analyzed their physical properties (structural, magnetic, thermodynamic, and mechanical), and used them to build electromagnetic machines like electromagnets and transformers.

Experimental details

The composites were prepared from Fe powder with a grain size below 63 μm (supplied by Progmars, Leszno, Poland) and acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) Starex HF-0660IW (from Lotte Chemicals, Seoul, South Korea), melt flow rate of 3.5 g/cm^3 (200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$; 5.0 kg). The ABS pellets were melted and blended with Fe powder in METALCHEM 20–32D (IMPiB, Toruń, Poland) single-screw machine, the machine screw was equipped with a tip that intensifies the mixing process. The extruder barrel temperature profile was set as follows: 210-230-240-250-250(die) $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

After exiting the extruder head, the extrude material was cooled and continuously pelletized by means of a milling granulator. Fe and ABS were mixed in different weight ratios. Composites with mass Fe content of 50%, 66% and 75% were produced. The choice of concentrations was dictated by the desire to get as highest magnetization as possible, on the other hand we know that too much Fe will make the material too brittle to be printable. From the composites produced, a filaments with a diameter of 1.75 ± 0.05 mm were produced using single screw extruder METALCHEM 20-32D (IMPiB, Toruń, Poland) the finished material was wound on spools with a winder. A commercially available filament from PROTOPASTA (Protoplant, Inc, Vancouver, WA, Canada) consisting of Fe particles (44%) and polylactide (PLA) was used as a reference material.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) data were collected at room temperature (RT) on X'pert Pro (Malvern Panalytical Ltd, Malvern, UK) diffractometer using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ -radiation, generated at 40 kV and 30 mA ($\lambda = 1.5418\text{\AA}$), in Bragg-Brentano geometry.

The samples' densities were assessed using the Archimedes method, employing an electronic balance XA 110.4Y.A from Radwag (Radom, Poland) and ethanol as the medium. Measurements were made at room temperature. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) imaging and energy dispersive

X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) is carried out on a NovaNanoSEM 230 FE-scanning (FEI, Hillsboro, OR, USA) electron microscope equipped with Apollo X Silicon Drift Detector.

DC Magnetization measurements were carried out using a Physical Properties Measurement System (PPMS) from Quantum Design (San Diego, CA, USA) with vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) option in in magnetic fields up to 1.2 T at 300 K.

The heat capacity (C_p) was measured in the same PPMS with the 2τ relaxation technique. The sample was attached to the puck platform with the use of Apiezon N grease.

A broadband dielectric spectrometer Alpha-A High-Performance Frequency Analyzer (Novocontrol GmbH, Montabaur, Germany) was used to measure the electrical conductivity in the frequency range of 1 Hz – 1 MHz, with voltage oscillations of ± 1 V.

Mechanical strength measurements were investigated by universal testing machines Zwick/Roell Z010 (ZwicRoell GmbH & Co. KG, Ulm, Germany). 3D bar shaped ($80 \times 10 \times 4$ mm³) specimens were tested in bending mode with bending speed 2 mm/min for modulus measurement and 10 mm/min for the rest of the measurement. The measurements for each material were repeated three times.

A 3D printer Prusa i3 MK3S+ (Prusa Research a.s., Prague, Czech Republic) was used to print parts. For ABS-based materials, the nozzle temperature was 250°C, the heatbed temperature was set at 60°C, while for PLA-based composite the nozzle temperature was reduced to 225°C maintaining the 60°C of the bed platform temperature. The printing speed for most samples was about 20 mm/min. G-code files were generated in the Slic3r Prusa Edition program. The 3d printed samples were prepared with 100 % infill density.

Result and Discussion

Structural characterization

We conducted detailed structural testing on the materials we produced at various scales. The XRD measurement results were performed for the starting materials, fabricated composites and a commercial sample. The results of these measurements are shown in Fig 1, together with the model

diffraction pattern for α -Fe (space groups $Im\bar{3}m$, no. 229) [16]. The graph clearly shows that in all composites the crystallographic structure of α -Fe has been preserved and there are no traces of Fe oxides or any other contamination. The XRD pattern for ABS in the low angle range shows two broad peaks is typical for an amorphous material. The process of preparing the composites does not affect the crystallographic structure of Fe. Measurements of the commercial material from PROTOPASTA showed that it also contained particles of crystalline α -Fe. We observed that the intensity of the diffraction peaks for the composite materials differs from that predicted by the theoretical model. For each sample, we calculated the ratio of the intensity of the (200) and (211) peaks to the intensity of the main (110) peak. These ratios were found to be 2 to 4 times higher than those predicted by the theoretical model. We believe this discrepancy is due to the texture formed during the composite synthesis process. Texture can significantly affect the physical properties of the materials [17]. The average size of the Fe crystallites was calculated using the Scherrer equation [18], $D = K\lambda/\beta\cos\theta$, where λ is the X-ray wavelength, β is the peak width of the diffraction peak profile at half maximum height, θ is the Bragg angle, and $K = 0.9$ is a shape parameter. D value was of approximately 18 nm for all samples. Also for the PROTOPASTA sample, the D value was ~ 18 nm. This indicates that the Fe particles are polycrystalline in nature.

Figure 1. X-ray diffraction patterns for pure Fe powder, ABS, and composite samples of Fe/ABS and Fe/PLA (PROTOPASTA). The bottom panel shows the theoretical diffraction pattern for pure α -Fe, with the most prominent peaks labeled by their Miller indices.

The composite surface underwent examination to investigate the dispersion of Fe particles within the composite material. The images in the top row of Fig. 2 show the surfaces of the studied samples. These images are blurred due to the electrical charging of the plastics in the electron beam of the microscope. Nevertheless, it appears that the samples are homogeneous with no obvious gas gaps or cracks. Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) mapping indicated that the Fe particles were quite evenly distributed throughout the polymer. For the sample with the highest Fe content, we observed that the particles tend to agglomerate in some places. The average size of the Fe particles, as determined by electron microscopy imaging, measured at $\sim 60 \mu\text{m}$, demonstrating good alignment with the expected values. Furthermore, alongside the predominant nominal-sized particles, a multitude of smaller Fe particles were also observed. Fe particles have a rather irregular shape, in most imaged cases it can be compared to an irregular ellipsoid.

Figure 2. SEM images (upper row) and EDS elemental mapping (lower row) of the surface of studied Fe/ABS and Fe/PLA (PROTOPASTA) composites. Please note the slightly different magnification for different samples. The red color on the EDS maps represents the iron (Fe).

When the density value of a given material is known, the weight and dimensions of the object that will be constructed from the material can be determined. The value of density of composites ρ_c changes with increasing Fe concentration x (see Fig. 3). As can be seen from the graph, the density of the tested materials does not change linearly. Thus, it does not satisfy the empirical rule of mixtures [19] for the upper-bound limit: $\rho_c = \rho_{Fe}x + \rho_{ABS}(1-x)$, where ρ_{Fe} is density of pure Fe, and ρ_{ABS} is density of pure ABS, and x is Fe concentration. The ρ_c is closer to that of pure ABS than that of pure Fe for all studied x , and obtained data can be nicely fitted using lower-bound limit of rule of mixtures [19]: $\rho_c = (x/\rho_{Fe} + (1-x)/\rho_{ABS})^{-1}$. The density of the PROTOPASTA (1.85 g/cm^3) is greater than for pure PLA (1.24 g/cm^3 [20]) and similar to the density of the ABS-based composite with 66% Fe.

At the macro-scale, the composites exhibited different surface roughness and brittleness depending on the Fe concentration. The composite with the highest Fe content had the roughest surface and was the most brittle.

Figure 3. Density of Fe/ABS composites. The solid red line represent the values obtained from rules of mixtures. The dashed line indicates the density of the PROTOPASTA (Fe/PLA composite) material.

Magnetic properties

We used a vibrating sample magnetometer to determine the magnetic properties. Pure polymers such as PLA and ABS exhibit diamagnetic properties, which means their contribution to magnetic properties is insignificant. All Fe-based composite materials show characteristics of soft magnetic properties, indicating their ability to easily magnetize and demagnetize. At 300 K, we observed an absence of a hysteresis loop in the magnetic materials, suggesting no residual magnetization. This observation was made under a magnetic field of approximately 1 T, leading to the saturation magnetization of all materials in the experimental setup. The process of preparing the composites does not affect the magnetic properties of Fe. As the iron content decreases, the maximum magnetization value also decreases linearly, and the magnetic permeability decreases accordingly (see inset of Fig. 4). Adjusting the Fe content in the composite allows for fine-tuning of its magnetic properties. We determined the magnetization value (M_S) at $T = 300$ K and a magnetic field strength of 1 T for all samples and recorded the values in Table 1. The Fe content obtained from comparing the magnetization values for pure Fe and the magnetization of composites $M_S/M_S(\text{Fe})$ correlates well with

the nominal Fe content, confirming good control over sample quality. The magnetic properties of the PROTOPASTA commercial sample closely resemble our 50% Fe sample.

Figure 4. Magnetic properties of studied materials: Fe/ABS composite with different Fe content, pure Fe powder, pure ABS (shown as an orange dot, $x = 0$, in inset), and commercial material from PROTOPASTA (Fe/PLA composite). Magnetization curves $M(\mu_0H)$ were measured at 300 K. Inset shows the magnetization value determined for a magnetic field of 1 T (M_S) for different composites as a function of Fe concentration. The red solid line represents a linear fit.

Table 1. Physical properties of Fe/ABS and Fe/PLA (PROTOPASTA) composites: ρ - density, M_S - maximum value of magnetization measured in the magnetic field of 1 T and at $T = 300$ K, $M_S/M_S(\text{Fe})$ - the ratio of the maximum value of magnetization of composites to the magnetization of pure Fe, C_p - specific heat at $T = 290$ K, σ_{AC} - AC electrical conductivity at $T = 293$ K for $\nu = 1$ Hz, E - Young's modulus, σ_{fC} - flexural strength, σ_{fM} - maximum flexural strength.

SAMPLE	ρ (g/cm ³)	M_S (emu/g) @ 1 T		C_p (J/gK) @ 290 K	σ_{AC} $\times 10^{-14}$ (S/cm) @ 293 K	E (MPa)	σ_{fC} (MPa)	σ_{fM} (MPa)
		$M_S/M_S(\text{Fe})$						

100% Fe	7.87(1)	212(1)	100%	0.45(1)	-	-	-	-
75% Fe	3.16(1)	170(1)	80%	0.75(2)	12.4(1)	-	-	-
66% Fe	1.95(1)	133(1)	63%	0.72(2)	4.2(1)	3320(298)	-	42(2)
50% Fe	1.33(1)	106(1)	50%	0.88(2)	1.4(1)	2280(261)	-	21(1)
PROTOPASTA	1.85	94(1)	44%	0.85(2)	0.4(1)	4090(32)	83(4)	85(1)

Specific heat measurements

Knowing the specific heat (C_p) of a material helps us determine the amount of heat energy needed to increase its temperature. In 3D printing, heating the material lowers its viscosity. Therefore, the material with lower specific heat requires less energy for the 3D printing process. The C_p of ABS is relatively high (1.5 J/gK at 300 K [21]), which makes it difficult to heat treat and 3D print. ABS is more difficult to machine than PLA, which has lower specific heat (0.86 J/gK at 300 K [22]). As seen in Fig. 5 adding Fe powder lowers the specific heat value of composites. The C_p values for the tested materials and starting materials at 290 K are summarized in Table 2. The addition of 50% Fe reduces the specific heat to less than 0.9 J/gK at 300 K. As the specific heat value decreases, the melting point should also decrease, which will facilitate the 3D printing process. The specific heat value of the composite with 66% Fe and 75% Fe is lower than the specific heat of the commercial PROTOPASTA material. By controlling the content of Fe particles in the composite, we can easily regulate the C_p value of the entire composite. This can help in reducing the energy consumption of the printer and in obtaining materials with higher thermal conductivity [23]. A similar effect was observed in ABS-based composites with much lower Fe content (10% -20%) in the previous work [24].

Figure 5. The specific heat of Fe/ABS and Fe/PLA composites (PROTOPASTA) is depicted using full symbols, alongside the pure components Fe, ABS, and PLA (data for polymers are from the literature) at room temperature (indicated by dashed lines).

Electric properties

The AC electric conductivity (σ'_{AC}) of composites was examined using impedance spectroscopy. Figure 6 displays the frequency (ν) dependence of electric conductivity $\sigma'_{AC}(\nu)$ across all measured frequencies, ranging from 1 Hz to 1 MHz. The electric conductivity of Fe/ABS composites varies with frequency, increasing as the frequency goes up. The slope of the conductivity is close to 1, and the AC electrical conductivity rises with an increase in frequency without exhibiting a DC plateau. No DC conductivity can be measured, so even in the sample with the highest Fe content, the percolation limit was not reached. This is a typical electrical response observed not only in polymers and composites but also in other disordered solid conductors [25]. Pure ABS is a strong electrical insulator [26]. Compared to pure ABS, the conductivity value of the composites studied increased by approximately two orders of magnitude, from $\sim 10^{-16}$ to $\sim 10^{-14}$ S/cm. Exemplary calculated values of electric conductivity for a given frequency ($\nu = 1$ Hz) are depicted in the inset of Figure 6. The figure shows that the increasing amount of Fe alters the electric properties, leading to

exponential increase in electric conductivity value, from $1.5(1) \times 10^{-16}$ S/cm (for pure ABS) [26] to $1.2(1) \times 10^{-13}$ S/cm (for composite sample with 75% Fe) at a temperature of 293 K. The observed trend is clearly different from, for example, the ABS and permalloy (Py—Ni₇₅Fe₂₀Mo₅) based composite, where electrical conductivity clearly increases only for significant Py contents (80%) [27]. The sample with the highest concentration of Fe demonstrates the greatest conductivity across all frequencies. Through the use of more Fe, the electrical resistance of the composites can be further reduced. Compared to PLA-based composites, the tested materials have better electrical conductivity. At room temperature and frequency 1 Hz, the σ'_{AC} value for PROTOPASTA is $4.1(1) \times 10^{-15}$ S/cm. The lower electrical conductivity for PLA-based composites is mainly due to their lower Fe content (44%) compared to ABS-based composites.

Figure 6. Dependence of AC electrical conductivity on frequency $\sigma'_{AC}(\nu)$ for Fe/ABS and Fe/PLA (PROTOPASTA) composites measured at 293 K. Inset shows the dependence of σ_{AC} as a function of Fe concentration (x) for $\nu = 1$ Hz. Notice semi-log scale. The value for pure ABS (shown as an orange dot, $x = 0$) was obtained from literature [26].

Mechanical properties

In order to check the mechanical strength of the materials obtained, we performed bending measurements. Figure 7 shows the dependence of stress (σ) as a function of strain (ε) for two composite specimens and a specimen made of commercial material. Measurements for the sample with 75% Fe were impossible due to its brittleness, therefore the measurements were made only for samples with 50% and 66% Fe. For ABS-based samples, only a range of elastic deformation with a linear $\sigma(\varepsilon)$ relationship was observed. For the PLA-based sample, both elastic and plastic deformation regions were observed outside the elastic region. The PLA-based material has higher strength as it has the highest stress value at rupture. It is also more tougher because the area under the stress vs strain curve is the largest. The greater slope of the curve in the elastic strain region also suggests that it is more rigid. The observed differences in mechanical properties of studied materials are mainly due to the use of different polymers [28]. To enhance the mechanical properties, it is necessary to make appropriate adjustments to the Fe content, particle size, and/or consider altering the type of plastic. Previous studies have demonstrated that the mechanical properties of ABS-based composites and magnetic materials are significantly influenced by the size of the filler particles [29]. It has been observed that composites containing smaller particles maintain thermoplastic properties. Thus, it is reasonable to assume that using smaller Fe particles can enhance the mechanical properties of ABS and Fe-based composites.

Values of determined Young modulus (E) and flexural strength (σ_{fC}) for the tested materials are collected in Table 1. It is worth noting that they are similar to the parameters for pure plastics; for pure ABS: $E = 1790 - 3200$ MPa and $\sigma_{fC} = 41-75$ MPa [30], and for pure PLA: $E = 3600$ MPa [31] and $\sigma_{fC} = 60-80$ MPa [32]. According to our tests, adding 50-66% of Fe does not significantly impact the mechanical properties of pure ABS. We have not noticed any deterioration or improvement in ABS properties within the studied composition range. Previous studies on Fe/ABS composites with lower Fe content have shown a slight increase in stiffness [24]. It's important to note that the lack of significant changes may be related to printing parameters (layer thickness, printing speed), as earlier findings have demonstrated a clear relationship between printing parameters and mechanical properties [33]. The material not only affects the mechanical properties of the test object, but since the

specimens for the bending test were printed, it is expected that various types of imperfections (e.g. voids) will weaken the test piece mechanically, as already observed in the literature for other similar systems [34].

It is also worth mentioning that due to the low-scale nature of the work, the procedure for making the composite mixture was not performed on a twin-screw machine, therefore the level of homogenization of the structure is certainly much worse for ABS-based materials, which certainly has a significant impact on the possible level of deformation of the material structure and the resulting mechanical characteristic. In the current phase of work, this aspect of the properties does not seem important, because the key parameters related to the measurement of magnetoelectric parameters are possible even for samples with relatively low mechanical performance. Further work related to improving the dispersion and compatibilization of the matrix-filler system may constitute one of the stages of pre-implementation work.

Figure 7. Mechanical properties of 3D printable composites. Stress σ vs. strain ϵ curves of Fe/ABS and Fe/PLA (PROTOPASTA) composite materials. The measurements for each material were repeated three times.

Electromagnetic devices

After carefully studying the physical properties of the material we produced, we decided to use it to print electromagnetic device components. The construction of electromagnetic devices involved creating 3D models of components using CAD software. These models were then converted into printer-readable files. The components were printed using filaments made from different composites with a diameter of 1.75 mm. 3D printing parts from composites is a difficult task, requiring a balance between different technological parameters that often compete with each other [35]. The 3D printed parts were used to fabricate objects with magnetic properties due to the addition of Fe powder. For our study, we chose commonly used devices with a relatively simple design. However, even for these devices, using additive manufacturing to produce them can bring many benefits [36].

The first device created was an electromagnet (Fig. 8a). The electromagnet consisted of a C-shaped 3D printed core measuring $40\text{ mm} \times 40\text{ mm} \times 10\text{ mm}$, with a coil of copper wire inside. The coil had a 1156 turns. When an electric current of 5V and 160 mA flowed through the coil, the electromagnet's plunger was activated, demonstrating that the device worked. Although the force acting on the plunger was not large, the functionality of the device was proven.

The second device that was constructed is a toroidal transformer (Fig.8b). The transformer was built using a 3D printed ring with an outer diameter of 50 mm and an inner diameter of 40 mm. The primary and secondary windings were made of copper wire and contained 100 and 200 turns, respectively. The use of 3D printed elements enabled the construction of functional electromagnetic devices. Furthermore, a special test bench has been set up to characterize the built transformers. The results of the measurements for three different devices constructed from 3D printed elements using various magnetic composites are shown in Figure 9. The graphs illustrate that all three devices exhibit similar characteristics, indicating that each of the three tested composites is suitable for constructing such devices.

Figure 8. Photographs of devices constructed from components printed on a 3D printer using manufactured Fe/ABS composites: **a** electromagnet and **b** transformer.

It should be noted that the performance of the built devices is significantly inferior to identical ones but made of traditional materials and in a traditional way [36]. Nevertheless, 3D printing can be done very fast with a single device in home conditions. It is not difficult to imagine that there will be niches in which such devices, with slightly different parameters, will find applications. An important advantage, so made devices will be their much lower weight.

Moreover, these are just demonstration examples, it is not difficult to imagine other applications where geometrical customization is more required, and where getting details using FDM of magnetically soft materials will be important [35,37].

Figure 9. Characteristics of transformers with a core printed on a 3D printer from various Fe/ABS and Fe/PLA (PROTOPASTA) composites. Current dependence of voltage U_{pp} **a** and magnetic induction B **b** for constructed devices.

Conclusions

In this work, we developed and examined a new composite based on ABS polymer and Fe powder, which is suitable for 3D printing. A magnetic composite based on ABS plastic and Fe powder was prepared and described in detail. Structural measurements showed that the Fe particles are evenly distributed in the plastic matrix and do not agglomerate. Fe did not oxidize during the composite synthesis process and retains its magnetic properties. The magnetization of the composites changes linearly with the change in Fe content. The addition of Fe reduced the specific heat of ABS by almost three times. The prepared composites are electrical insulators for which the electrical resistance is of the order of 10^{14} Ohm/cm. The prepared Fe- and ABS-based composites proved to be brittle and with negligible ductility, which may limit their application. Magnetic core components were printed from the resulting composites of 50% and 66% Fe and demonstrated proper operation of simple electromagnetic transducers. It should be highlighted here, that magnetic permeability of the 3D printed core is lower comparing to laminated core. Nevertheless presented results allows to state that 3D printing technology is opening up new possibilities in the construction of electromagnetic devices.

Further research on Fe/ABS composites could lead to materials with unique properties that will find applications in many fields (e.g. for contactless magnetic field driven switches) and expand the possibilities for magnetic materials.

Data availability statement

The data that supports the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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